

Tier II Cities- The Emerging Geographical Choice For A Sustainable Software Industry In India

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Abstract

This paper is an attempt to bring out the common factors responsible for making certain Tier-II cities the emerging magnets for the software industry in India. At first the paper investigates, which Tier-II cities are leading when it comes to investments in software industry. The basic objective of this study is to bring out the factors that have helped these Tier II cities to emerge as the new IT hubs, which then could be prescribed to other state governments to attract more investors and companies to prospective cities of their states. In this paper, the metropolitan cities are termed as Tier-I and other major economic cities/capitals of the country as Tier-II. The analysis is based on the information procured from various recent surveys, reports, government policy documents and digital databases. The data so obtained are illustrated using graphs, charts and tables. On a broad level, this paper concludes that factors such as location of a SEZ/Tech-City, an attractive IT policy by the state government, quality of life, diversity in population of the city, perception of security, infrastructure, research & educational environment, urban planning and a sense of empowered political representation with transparency and accountability in governance have been instrumental in making these cities the sustainable choice for future growth of software industry.

Keywords : Tier II cities, IT Policy, Software Industry, Emerging Geographical Choice and Quality of Life.

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1 Introduction

According to [Venkatesh, 2017] The Indian IT-BPM (Information Technology-Business Process Management) industry is projected to grow at a rate of 8.6% (in constant currency) to reach over \$ 155 billion by end of FY17. The IT-BPM exports from India is expected to reach \$ 118 billion and the domestic IT-BPM market is expected to grow by 12 percent to reach Rs 2,545 billion. Currently, the industry employs 3.86 million people. India is also gaining prominence in terms of intellectual capital with several global IT firms setting up their innovation centres in India. India ranks third among global start-up ecosystems with more than 4,200 start-ups [IBEF, 2017].

All this potential growth in the IT/Software sector encourages us to find which regions will benefit from this growth in future. In previous decades the major benefactor of this sector growth has been the Tier I metropolitan cities of the country i.e. a) National Capital Region b) Mumbai c) Kolkata d) Bangalore e) Pune f) Hyderabad & g) Chennai [Wikipedia, 2017]. This dominance of Tier-I cities is evident from the data in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Today these Tier-I cities are experiencing an immense burden of overpopulation and hence are becoming inadequate in providing infrastructural needs for the aspiring companies. Long commute hours, inflation and poor amenities have become major reasons for a lot of physical and mental stress in these Tier-I cities. These prominent signs tells us that metropolitan cities are now reaching a saturation point [Jain, 2017]. Hence the focus is shifting to find the next best destination, that is Tier II cities. But the question is will the Tier II cities be able to move up quickly, will they be able to grab a bigger pie and carve a space of their own.

According to The Digital Indian Cities Survey, 2016, [Damodaran, 2016] which was developed and conducted by the CEOWORLD Magazine and includes responses from more than 74,000 IT professionals and tech recruiters, all over India to find the Best-perceived tech cities in India, we find that Ahmedabad is at number seven, Thiruvananthapuram is at eight while Jaipur is at number nine (Table no.1). As we can see only these three Tier II cities are performing at par with metropolitan cities in top 10 cities. In this paper we will try and analyze what are the reasons that they are leading the pack of Tier-II cities.

But before moving ahead there was a need to confirm the findings of Digital India Survey. For that a study was conducted. In this study we took help of a report by ESC(Electronics and Computer Software Export Promotion Council) on computer software and ITes Export [Electronics and Council, 2017]. In the report by ESC, the contribution of various states of India in software export was mentioned (in percentage basis). Among all the mentioned states, we have removed the states in which the Tier I cities are located and the states whose

Table 1: Best-perceived tech cities in India (Ranked over various parameters)

Overall Rank	City	Startup Ecosystem	Tech Infra	Innovation	Livability	Growth	Tier I or Tier II
1	Bangalore, Karnataka	1	2	1	3	2	Tier I
2	Delhi NCR	2	1	2	2	1	Tier I
3	Mumbai, Maharashtra	4	3	4	6	5	Tier I
4	Hyderabad, Telangana	3	4	3	5	4	Tier I
5	Pune, Maharashtra	6	9	5	7	6	Tier I
6	Ahmedabad, Gujarat	5	7	7	4	3	Tier II
7	Chennai, Tamil Nadu	7	5	6	8	8	Tier I
8	Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala	10	10	10	11	7	Tier II
9	Jaipur, Rajasthan	8	6	8	9	9	Tier II
10	Kolkata, West Bengal	11	12	12	12	10	Tier I

Source: The Digital Indian Cities Survey, 2016, [Damodaran, 2016] which was developed and conducted by the Ceoworld Magazine.

contribution to the total export from India is less than 0.01%. This was done to make a clear picture of emerging states.

The result thus obtained is depicted on Figure 1, which is a graph illustrating the performance of the states. The inferences thus found were much similar to the Digital India Survey, that Kerala is performing well followed by Gujarat and Rajasthan. The success in these states can be assumed to be primarily from cities like Thiruvananthapuram for Kerala, Ahmedabad for Gujarat and Jaipur for Rajasthan. Hence we can fairly say that in particular these three cities are performing better than other Tier II cities as far as software industry is concerned.

Even “According to EY’s India Attractiveness Survey 2015, 26 percent of investor group rated Ahmedabad as India’s leading emerging city, followed by Jaipur at 13 percent.”

Ernst and Young conducts India Attractiveness Survey to examine the attractiveness of a particular region as an investment destination. They adopt a two-step methodology analyses for both the reality and perception of FDI in the respective region. Their Findings are based on the views of representative panels of international and local opinion leaders and decision-makers [Ernst and Young, 2015].

Figure 1: Performance of certain states of India analyzed in terms of percentage of total Exports by India over the years

Hence to understand what do Tier-II cities have to do to move up the ladder, we can go into details of what has been done by these three Tier-II cities to be on the top position among Tier-II cities.

2 Introduction about these Cities

Ahmedabad is a manufacturing hub located in Gujarat. It is home to some of the leading export and trading companies. In 2010, Forbes magazine rated Ahmedabad as the fastest-growing city in India [Kotkin, 2010].

Thiruvananthapuram is the capital city of the state of Kerala. It remained at the top of the Annual Survey of India's City-Systems (ASICS) [Janaagraha, 2017], where major parameters included urban planning and design, urban capacities and resources, empowered and legitimate political representation, transparency, accountability and participation.

Jaipur, the capital of Rajasthan is fast picking up as an attractive investment destination, owing to investor friendly policies, and its proximity to Delhi. Jaipur emerged as a favourite among first-time investors, particularly in telecom and IT-enabled services [Ernst and Young, 2015].

3 Factors affecting success of these Tier-II cities

3.1 Location of a Major IT City/SEZ in the City

The presence of a Major IT City/SEZ nearby the city provide a major boost in making a city attractive for investors. As for investors an IT City/SEZ means a specialized area with fiscal incentives and availability of good infrastructures where industries could be established with less hassle and can start early. For the city a IT City/SEZ means employees and companies bringing an infusion of wealth into the entire region through secondary service activities like retail, hospitality, transportation, financial services and so on [Aggarwal, 2006].

Gujarat International Finance Tec-City is an under-construction central business district between Ahmedabad and Gandhinagar which will be built on 359 hectares of land to provide high quality physical infrastructure to financial and technical firms. It will have a special economic zone (SEZ), international education zone, integrated townships, an entertainment zone, hotels, a convention centre, an international techno park, Software Technology Parks of India (STPI) units, shopping malls, stock exchanges and service units.

Technopark located in Thiruvananthapuram, is the largest Information Technology park in Asia in terms of built up area. Launched in 1990, Technopark as of 2015 is home to over 350 companies, employing nearly 60,000 professionals. Technopark also hosts a Technology Business Incubation Cell who has given rise to over 47 successful ventures. Technopark hosts two educational and research institutes, The Indian Institute of Information Technology and Management–Kerala (IIITM–K) and the Asian School of Business.

Mahindra World City (Jaipur) Ltd is an important SEZ located in Jaipur. It was started in 2007 and was built in a PPP between the Mahindra Group and RIICO (a Govt. of Rajasthan undertaking). It has software companies like Appirio India, Wipro, Genpact, Infosys, Metlife, Nagarro, Nucleus, Q3 Infotech, DBOI Global, EXL Solutions, Girnar Software, ISYS Softech, Soncoya Solutions, Systweak Software, etc. The other major SEZs in Jaipur are Genpact Infrastructure (Jaipur) Pvt. Ltd. and Sitapura SEZ.

3.2 Diversity and Perception of Security

In a software company people from varying backgrounds come to work together in an open and friendly environment, hence there is always an indirect demand from the city to be welcoming to these people from diverse background. Therefore the companies always seek a city that is tolerant in terms of diversity and a city which feels safe & secure to reside in [Florida, 2003].

Other than depicted in figure 2b, Ahmedabad is also home to some 2000 Parsis and some 125 members of the Bene Israel Jewish community. According to [Janaagraha, 2017],

Ahmedabad is the second safest city in India while Jaipur is ranked at 9th position. In Thiruvananthapuram, city centre, there is a mosque, a temple and a Christian church next to each other as neighbours, establishing the communal harmony of Keralites. Thiruvananthapuram hosts Malayalam, English, Tamil, Tulu, Kannada, Konkani, Dhivehi, Hindi, Telugu, and Urdu speakers.

To check about safety of a city, in this paper a comparison analysis of certain Tier-II Cities was done. We took ratio of Total Cognizable Crimes under IPC over population to check how safe a city is.

(a) Ratio of Total Cognizable Crimes under IPC over Population of certain Tier-II Cities.

(b) A Bar chart depicting the religious communities residing in the city (in percentage terms)

Source: Crime Statistics, Ministry of Home Affairs.

Source: India Census 2011 and Wikipedia.

Figure 2: Charts depicting Diversity and Perception of Security of the three cities under consideration.

The findings are depicted on Figure 2a. Ahmedabad’s ratio of the year 2012 was 3.23, for the year 2013 was 3.08 and for the year 2014 was 2.11. Which was least among all. Hence we can say that Ahmedabad is one of the safest cities in India.

3.3 Urban Infrastructure, Governance and Quality of Life

For a software company, client and skilled employee are of paramount importance. In present work culture, what looks good sells more. Therefore, there are so many advertising agencies, PR firms, office interiors firms, etc. working day and night. All this to create an impression on the client and employee. To complement this impression, the software company needs the city to be good in terms of infrastructure, governance and quality of life, so that the impression on clients can improve and the employees are attracted to live in a city which promises good quality of life and governance [Sahoo and Dash, 2009].

According to [LLC, 2012], Ahmedabad is one of the fastest growing cities in India in terms of infrastructure and attracting investments. Ahmedabad was ranked best city in

India in terms of civic infrastructure, second in terms of city investing adequate funds in public infrastructure and services and third on the basis of quality of life and in terms of how well a city address its citizen's complaint by the survey done by [Janaagraha, 2017].

One major point in case of Infrastructure of Jaipur according to [Janaagraha, 2017] is the - Rajasthan Urban Land (Certification of Titles) Bill. It improved the ability of urban property holders and governments to capitalize land holdings efficiently. Hence Cost advantage is of 20-40% in Commercial Real Estate compared to tier-1 locations.

According to [Janaagraha, 2017] Thiruvananthapuram is the most democratic perceived city of the country and is the best city in case of addressing citizen complaints. In the same report Thiruvananthapuram was rated as the best city in the country to live in for the second consecutive year.

3.4 Hospitality Sector

Usually in a software firms clients are both domestic and international. Therefore there is a demand of good Hospitality sector from the city. This sector is even required for client interactions, conferences and meetings.

In case of Ahmedabad from 519 classified hotel rooms in 2006-07, by 2014 Ahmedabad had almost 2,500 classified hotel rooms ranging from five-star to mid-scale and economy hotels. The compounded annual room inventory growth was of almost 30 per cent which is one of the highest among Indian cities [Biz, 2014a].

Jaipur with its forts, royal palaces, architecture and rich hospitality of the people has been a sought after tourist destination in the country. On the business side one can easily see the growth in no. of conferences and meetings conducted in the city. Hence, in the last few years the city has seen mushrooming of hotels of both domestic and international chains, to cater to such business side [Biz, 2014b].

The Department of Tourism, Government of Kerala recently won The Pacific Asia Travel Association (PATA) Grand and Gold Award 2017 for its Film Tourism Brochure in the Marketing Media – Consumer Travel Brochure category. This is backing the fact that Kerala is improving over the years as tourist destination hinting that this has paced the hospitality sector in Thiruvananthapuram.

3.5 Transportation Sector

Although clients can use Internet to communicate. But using Internet lacks the eye to eye contact and co-presence, the two important factors that develop the emotional commitment and trust between the two parties. This trust is very important. Therefore to fulfill this requirement of co-presence there is quite frequent visits, frequent meetings and sometimes

direct communication [Leamer and Storper, 2014]. This makes transportation and approach of a city an important consideration for selection by software companies as destinations.

In List of top 50 busiest airports of India by passenger traffic (domestic and international) for fiscal year 2016-17, Ahmedabad's 'Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel International Airport' is ranked at 8th position, Jaipur International Airport at 14th and Trivandrum International Airport is at 12th position. This list includes the Tier I metropolitan cities of India.

A new airport by the name of Dholera International Airport is proposed to be built near Navagam in the Dholera taluka of Ahmedabad district. It will be the largest airport in India with a total area of 7,500 hectares. Ahmedabad is well connected to other parts of India through rail and road. Ahmedabad Metro is an under construction mass-transit rail system for the cities of Ahmedabad and Gandhinagar. Phase-1 of this project is expected to complete by 2020. Ahmedabad BRTS is the most successful BRTS project in India, it also won the most Sustainable Transport Award in the world (2010).

Jaipur International Airport has been declared as the World's Best Airport in the category of 2 to 5 million passengers per annum for 2015 according to Airports Council International. Jaipur Metro commenced commercial operation on 3 June 2015. Jaipur is also the headquarters of North Western Zone of Indian Railways.

3.6 Education, Research and Associations

Educational Institutes provide two important contribution in case of Software companies. One they provide human resource to these software firms on the other hand University-Industry Linkages support innovation and growth in software industry. Hence presence of good research and educational institute in geographical vicinity plays a positive role in enhancing growth and innovation environment in software industry [Basant and Chandra, 2007] [Katz, 1994].

In case of Ahmedabad the Major educational institutions include the Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad, the Adani Institute of Infrastructure Management, the National Institute of Design, the Entrepreneurship Development Institute of India, the L.D. College of Engineering and the Vishwakarma Government Engineering College. Many national academic and scientific institutions, such as the Physical Research Laboratory and the ISRO are also based in the city. GESIA (Gujarat Electronics & Software Industries Association) has played a key role in development of Gujarat as a major IT hub by recommending incentives and branding initiatives.

Jaipur has numerous universities, more than 80 Engineering colleges, 48 Business management institutes and various other colleges and institutes. Major institutions include University of Rajasthan, EIIM, Edusolutions Institute of Internet Marketing, Malviya Na-

tional Institute of Technology, Jaipur National University, Manipal University, The LNM Institute of Information Technology and IIS University.

Thiruvananthapuram is a major educational hub of Kerala. It is an academic and research focal point in the country with an array of premier institutions such as Vikram Sarabhai Space Centre, Liquid Propulsion Systems Centre, Indian Institute of Science Education and Research, National Institute For Interdisciplinary Science and Technology, Centre for Development Studies, Kerala Technical University, Indian Institute of Space Science and Technology and the National Centre for Earth Science Studies.

3.7 Government Policy

The progress of a region depends very much on the vision and policy of the government [Athreye, 2005]. The commitment of the government and the hassle free single window clearances for entrepreneurs. In following table there is a comparison analysis of different subsidies given by the different states for promotion of IT industry. The table is prepared from documents of IT Policy published by different states.

Table 2: IT Policy of the State Governments

S. No.	Subsidy Segment	Ahmedabad	Thiruvananthapuram	Jaipur
1	Capital Investment	Capital subsidy @ 25% of capital expenditure for one time purchase of Computers, networking and related hardware, subject to a ceiling of Rs. 1 crore.	30% of Fixed Capital Investment subject to a limit of Rs. 15 lakhs for companies located in Thiruvananthapuram.	Reimbursement of 50% of amount of VAT paid on purchase of plant and machinery or equipment for a period up to seven years.
2	Stamp Duty	100% reimbursement of Stamp Duty and Registration Fee for the first transaction.	Exemption from stamp duty upon executing lease/sale agreement.	Exemption from payment of 50% of Land Tax for seven years.
3	Power Tariff	Subsidy of Re. 1 per unit in the billed amount and 100% reimbursement for electricity duty for a period of five years.	IT/ITES units, IT parks and Akshaya e-centers are entitled to power tariff under HT1 or LT-IV tariff as applicable.	Exemption from payment of 50% of Electricity Duty for seven years.

S. No.	Subsidies Segment	Ahmedabad	Thiruvananthapuram	Jaipur
4	Patent Subsidy	Assistance at the rate of 50%, subject to a ceiling of Rs.2 lakhs per patent for domestic patents and Rs. 5 lakhs per patent for international patents.		Reimbursement of cost of filing patents for successfully receiving patents, limited to a maximum of Rs.3 lakh per patent awarded per year.

4 Conclusion

In this paper it was seen that three Tier II cities fared better than other Tier II cities of India when it comes to destination for Software industry in India. The reason for such favourite destination tag is due to these cities performance and improvements over the years in certain segments such as a) Quality of Life, b) Perception of Security, c) Infrastructure of the city, d) Educational Institutes and Research environment, e) Good transportation facilities (definitely an international airport), f) good hospitality sector, g) efforts of Associations, h) Convention centres, i) government positive effort in urban governance, j) urban planning and design, k) sense of empowered and legitimate political representation, and l) transparency and accountability in governance.

An attractive IT policy by the state government with good number of incentives and establishment of a SEZ or tech city can help catalyze the growth of IT sector rapidly. Hence state governments can improve these sectors in their capitals and prime Tier II cities to improve their share of pie in the IT sector growth in India.

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